

The Cult of Chinggis Khan (a.k.a. Genghis Khan) in Mongolia

By Dotno Pount, University of Pennsylvania

Entry tags: Mongolian Religions, Religious Group, Mongolian Shamanism, Shamanism, Buddhist Traditions, Inner Asian Native Religions, Mongolian Buddhism, Religious Practice

After Chinggis Khan (a.k.a. Genghis Khan) died in 1227, an assortment of his belongings were enshrined in his wives' palace tents (sg. *ordo*, pl. *ordos*, hence the English "horde"), and according to Mongolian tradition, became the locus of his continuing worship through the last eight centuries. The cult seems to have reached an apogee of power and importance in the 16-17th centuries, when Dayan Khan, a descendant of Qubilai Khan (a.k.a. Kublai Khan) and his house consolidated their rule. The tent shrines of Chinggis Khan was likely already a state shrine before this time, though the Great Khan did not necessarily control it (this is the "cult" referred to in the title, to be distinguished from the newfangled worship of Chinggis Khan and the Eternal Sky emerging across Inner Asia in the last three decades, about which Charleux, 2010, provides a great sketch). Simulacra of this cult still exist, at a colossal tourist attraction in the Ordos region of the Inner Mongolian Autonomous Region (IMAR) of China. There, to this day, hereditary shrine-custodians known as the Darkhad Mongols propitiate to Chinggis Khan, his family, and his banners. Although the turbulent 19th and 20th centuries saw repeated looting and destruction of the shrine's texts and treasured material relics, the Darkhad families managed to preserve the ritual programs and prayers in textual compilations known as the *Altan Bichig* (which means "Golden Writings").

Date Range: 1227 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mongolian-speaking region (East and North)

Region tags: Asia, North Asia

Roughly the eastern parts of Mongolian-speaking region where the prayers included in the Cult of Chinggis Khan corpus *Altan Bichig* (Golden Writings) are found either as cultic materials or independently (e.g., as fire-prayers), thus constituting a unified cultural area.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Bulag, Uradyn E. "Chapter 1: Hunting Chinggis Khan's Skull and Soul." In *Collaborative Nationalism: The Politics of Friendship on China's Mongolian Frontier*, 31–64. Asia/Pacific/Perspectives. Lanham, Md: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2010.

Notes: Bulag's discussion of Chinggis Khan's role in contemporary Inner Mongolian imaginary in Chapter 1 contains very important discussions of various aspects of the collective memory of the shrine's plight in the 20th century.

- Source 1: Atwood, Christopher Pratt. *Encyclopedia of Mongolia and the Mongol Empire*. New York: FactsOnFile, 2004. Pp. 161-165; under 'Eight White Yurts'.
- Source 2: Sayinjirgal, and Šaraldai. *Altan Ordon-u Tayilg-a*. Beijing: Ündüsüten-ü keblel-ün qoriy-a (Minzu Publishing House), 1983.
- Source 3: Yang, Haiying. "Kinsho" kenkyū e no josetsu. Suita-shi: Kokuritsu Minzokugaku Hakubutsukan, 1998.

Notes: For an overview in English on the cult, see Atwood (2004). Sayinjirgal and Šaraldai provide the best ethnographic account of the cult as their work is based on both their personal knowledge as members of the Darkhad community, as well as their extensive field research in the 1980s. For a sample of the Altan Bichig corpus (in facsimile and latin transliteration) and the introduction to the cult and its texts in Japanese see Yang (1998).

Reference: Yang, Haiying. "kinsho" Kenkyū E No Josetsu. Suita-shi: Kokuritsu Minzokugaku Hakubutsukan, 1998.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A345458424/AONE?u=upenn_main&sid=summon&xid=a84a6da0
- Source 1 Description: Bilik, N. (2013) 'The Worship of Chinggis Khan: Ethnicity, Nation-State and Situational Relativity', *China: An International Journal*, 11(2), pp. 25-41.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43193542>
- Source 2 Description: Charleux, Isabelle. "Chinggis Khan: Ancestor, Buddha or Shaman? On the Uses and Abuses of the Portrait of Chinggis Khan." *Mongolian Studies* 30/31 (2008): 207-58.
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.cjshl.com>
- Source 3 Description: Official website of the Chinggis Khan Mausoleum museum complex

Notes: While this article focuses on the historical and theological aspects of the Cult of Chinggis Khan, and does not cover some of the complex discourses surrounding this tradition today. The interested reader could read the anthropologist Naran Bilik's article on the dialectics between the cultic worship of Chinggis Khan and notions of ethnicity and the place of contemporary Inner Mongolians as citizens of the PRC. As for the renewed interest in and worship of Chinggis Khan in contemporary Mongolia, outside of the context of the historical Cult of Chinggis Khan covered in this article, see the excellent article by the art historian Isabelle Charleux. Moreover, the official website of the museum complex in Ordos is also a great resource for understanding not just the current activities at the cult, but for seeing the representation of this tradition in the website form by the authorities in Ordos.

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2829936940?accountid=14707>
- Source 1 Description: Pount, Dotno Dashdorj. "The Cult of Chinggis Khan in the Dayan Khanid Period." Order No. 30485843, University of Pennsylvania, 2023.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://altanbichig.wordpress.com/>

– Source 1 Description: Author's site where the critical edition of the Altan Bichig is to be made available in latinized transcription (under construction).

Notes: A critical edition along with translation is found in the author's dissertation cited above.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The contact between Buddhism and the Cult of Chinggis Khan is ambiguous, and the question competition cannot be answered in either the affirmative or negative without obscuring the complexity. Contemporary proponents of the Cult often claim that the interaction was competitive, and that "Buddhization" was akin to a hostile takeover, culturally speaking. See the article by Bilik, for example. However, one can easily see the Cult as having incorporated disparate elements from the Buddhist traditions that flourished in the Ordos region -- namely the Gelukpa school -- since the 16-17th centuries. In general, the Cult of Chinggis Khan does not identify itself as a "religion," as in a strictly doctrinally defined community with an organizational logic apart from the overall political system of the society. Therefore, its custodians could easily convert to Buddhism, build Buddhist temples for their local communities, and incorporate sacrifices made by monks among their ranks to the the rituals of the Chinggis Khan Cult without any concern that syncretism or adulteration of any sort has occurred. The concern of the Cult is in that sense orthogonal to the religious concerns of a community that the Buddhist sangha embeds itself in.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There are historical instances of murders and assassinations happening at or near the shrine, and the victims in each instance was a legitimate heir to the throne. The first instance is Muulan Qağan, who died at the hands of his own kingmaker Muuliqai Ong as a result of intrigue, stirred up by men of the Ordos. The fact that the Precious Summary (Erdeni-yin Tobči) places the coronation of Mulan as well as Muulikhai's prayer at the Chinggis Khan shrine suggests that in Ordos, there was memory of the cult having been under the control of the Qorčin, from which Muulikhai derives his pedigree. Almost two centuries later, the last Great Qağan, Ligdan, also seizes the cult from the Ordos, and takes it to Kökena'ur, to which he had retreated under pressure from the rising Jürchen and eastern Mongol coalition. The Ordos also made a stance decades after the Mulan Qağan episode by murdering the son of Dayan Qağan, who had sent his eldest to rule the Ordos as their ĵinong (viceroy). Therefore, the participants of the Chinggis Khan cult certainly have a long history of fighting over the control of the shrines, although whether other political motives are inextricably mired with their zeal to keep the shrines is beyond detailed analysis now.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The cult came under attack at least three times in recent centuries. First, the Dungan Rebellion (1862-1877) resulted in numerous combatants invading Ordos and raiding the locals as well as the cult. Later, in the post-Qing unraveling of civil order, bandits became ubiquitous in the region, and at least one group is remembered to have robbed the cult of its valuables. The memory is part of a cautionary tale, as that group of bandits soon met a series of uncanny misfortunes that convinced them to return the valuables. Then, during the Cultural Revolution, the cult's physical effects were burnt, and many of the Darqad community did not survive the purge.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: As the state cult, the shrine complex was by-definition supported by the state before the annexing of Mongolian principalities to the Qing Empire. During the Qing-period, the cult seems to have received imperial recognition around 1722, and especially beginning in 1765, the

current corpus of administrative documents of the cult come into existence, in which the Qing government's financial support of the cult becomes visible in the records. In the twentieth century, the cult also saw significant interference from state-actors. The Republic of China built a brick temple for the cult, but the Darkhad saw this as an ill omen, and tore it down years later. Then, many of the main shrines were moved farther west to Gansu in 1939, and Qinghai province in 1949, to keep the shrine away from first the Japanese, later the Chinese Communist Party forces. The Darkhad traveled to these locations in rotations from Ordos to service the shrines. Then, in 1954, Ulanfu (Ula'anküü), the ethnic Mongolian leading member of the Chinese Communist Party, arranged the shrines in exile to return to Ordos, and the Mausoleum was built. Although much of the shrines' physical objects were destroyed during the Cultural Revolution, since its end in 1979, the Mausoleum (now functioning as a museum), the scholarly efforts to document the shrine, and some roles of the Darkhad custodians have received state funding and government sanction.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):
– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: The process of choosing the next leader of the Darqad is known in modern times, in the late Qing period and the 20th century. The main element is, of course, being a scion of the right Darqad lineage. The other leading cult officiants choose their leader, the Tayiśi, and gets their nomination approved by the Qing Emperor. The j̄inong, up until the last century, was a hereditary position, and it appears that each successive j̄inong chose his own heir, and obtained approval from the Qing Emperor. We do not have data on how the leadership progression worked before modern times.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Sayinjirgal and Šaraldai (1982) gives examples of a 19th century cult leader who was accused of embezzlement, and was forced to resign.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– I don't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The term 'scripture' necessarily reminds one of the famous books of the Abrahamic faiths: the Old and New Testaments, the Quran, and other books that derive from the same tradition. For the Cult of Chinggis Khan, the core ritualistic books are neither origin stories nor theological justifications per se, but the liturgical texts to be recited at various rituals, the instructions for performing them, and the ritual codes for stipulating the sacrificial duty to the ritual community and the punishment for their violations. These texts are collectively called the "Altan Bičig," meaning "Golden Writings." They were once written in golden ink, as several of the colophons indicate, though the surviving manuscripts are mostly copies made by scholars in the 1960s on the eve of the Cultural Revolution in China, which resulted in the destruction of an enormous amount material heritage in Inner Mongolia, including the old manuscripts kept at the shrine. The "Altan Bičig" includes many prayers composed in the 18th century onwards by noted Buddhist clerical figures, such as the famous author, poet, translator and abbot monk Mergen Gegen. This is because the textual corpus has gradually accrued prayer texts, as the worshipping practices of the cult's officiants and participants changed across time. Moreover, although the texts defined as "scripture" may be reasonably limited to the "Altan Bičig," one must note the close textual relationships between its prayers and Mongolian historiography, as evidenced in the ubiquitous presence of the cult in histories such as the "Altan Tobči" (The Golden Summary; Bawden, 1955), "Erdeni-yin Tobči" (The Precious Summary; Elverskog, 2023), and "Śir-a Tuǰuǰi" (The Yellow Chronicle; no translations to English yet; for a translations to Russian, see Shastina, 1957; Tsendina, 2017) from the seventeenth century, and the sixteenth century history called the "Erdeni-yin Tunumul" (The Jewel Translucent Sutra; Elverskog, 2003). Many of the histories clearly incorporate the apocryphal tales about the eponymous founder found in the "Činggis Qaǰan-u Altan Tobči" (The Golden Summary of Chinggis Khan; Rogers, 2009), whose discursive relationship to the cult's oral history and legends is yet to be studied in detail. While these historical texts have been read out of the context of the cult so far, their close relationship with the liturgical texts passed down in the cult suggests that they are closely related to the worship of Chinggis Khan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1330 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1330 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The orality of the liturgies at the Cult is central, and even the written materials are either words that should be read/recited orally, or records and instructions on when to perform which prayers. However, the materials were certainly written down and transmitted in writing after a certain foundational period in the cult's history, and we can safely estimate that after the middle of the 17th century latest, all of the cult's orally performed prayers were written down. If written versions have always been a part of the cult officiants' repertory for preserving their memory, we have not found indisputable evidence for it from earlier times. Instead, we can only tell that some texts in the liturgical corpus are likely earlier than others, and that the ur-

form of the earliest one likely dates to the 1330s.

Reference: Pount, Dotno. "Chapter 3: A Pre-history of the Dayan Qaġanid Cult of Činggis Qan: The Ĵinong and the Ordo". PhD Dissertation. In *The Cult of Chinggis Khan in the Dayan Khanid Period*. Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania, 2023.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The reference to the "Horse Year Regulations" is found in the colophons of the texts that attribute the rules for offering sacrifices to Chinggis Khan, and the tradition in Ordos is that these were promulgated by Qubilai Qan" (Kublai Khan).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1260 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Qubilai Qan is considered a divine reincarnation of the Buddhist deity Manjūshri.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to obvious accruals of additional prayers in the liturgical collection Altan Bičig in the 18th and (possibly) 19th centuries, the corpus itself is meant to be modified as the new generations of the rulers of the Golden Lineage (descendants of Činggis Qan, but more specifically those of Dayan Qan) get added to the list of rulers. This is most obvious in the king-list prayer known as the "Yellow Book" (See Chapter 3 of Pount, 2023). Another way in which the corpus is subject to change is the modular structure of the rituals. There are many types of rituals for various occasions, including but not limited to seasonal ceremonies on specified dates, and ad-hoc occasions for people who want to give offerings. For each of these the ritual instructions would specify which prayers to recite in what order. Within certain prayers, there are also lines in which the name of the principal propitiator is inserted, and thus incorporated in the prayers addressing Činggis Qan. An example of a more recent alteration of the prayer texts include the texts adapted for the annual Činggis Qan Ceremony held in New Jersey by the Mongol American Cultural Association (MACA) by one of its founders, Gombojav Hangin. As his last name indicates, the late Mr. Gombojav was from the Hangin banner of Ordos, Inner Mongolia, and thus had an intimate knowledge of the cult. His modifications of the prayers adapts the ceremony to the need of the Mongolian diaspora in the United States.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The persons privy to performing the ceremonies were limited to the descendant sovereigns and the cult officiants for most of the cult's history. The prayer texts suggest that at a point when the Khan and the Jinong (viceroy) were principal propitiators of sacrificial ceremonies, while the Darqad officiants assisted them in their performance before 1634. Their roles were subsequently taken over by the j̄inongs, who continued to inherit the title from their fathers after the incorporation into the Qing Empire. Aside from the privilege to enunciate the prayers, divination played an important role in the rituals. According to the detailed ritual instructions excavated from the Darqan-Muuminggan banner in 1957 (See Pount, 2023), the interpretation of the portents involved the taste of the sacrificial foods. That is, the ruling elite who had the privilege to participate in the ceremonies and to receive the sacrificial foods constituted the institution that could interpret the result of the prayers -- namely, whether blessings are given or not. Furthermore, at the end of the White Herd Sačuli (libation sprinkling) ceremony, the participants divined using sheep entrails. This was interpreted by the officiant with the title Irögelci, meaning 'eulogizer', whereas the qan had to have whispered in the sheep's ear while it is alive. Other divination and interpretation practices mentioned in the texts and actually performed involve placing a cup upon the back of the reincarnate horse named White-as-Eggshell (Öndegen Čağan), and observing its orientation after it inevitably falls to the ground.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– I don't know

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Darqad lineages have actively maintained the scriptures through both writing copies and performing them, which involves memorizing the liturgies as well as performing the ritual acts with their bodies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: This, of course, refers to the tent-shrines and the sülde stands themselves. These are not quite "monuments" in the urban-sedentary cultural perspective, but their physical effect was largely the same.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Čomčağ tent-carts

Notes: Traditionally, mobile tents of the type called 'čomčağ' were used to house the shrines.

These look similar to the modern 'ger' (also known as 'yurt') from the outside, but are not collapsible. Instead they are permanently mounted onto large carts drawn by oxens or camels. The main tent-shrine for Činggis Qan and his chief queen Börte Qatun was composed of two connected čomčağs -- arranged front to back. According to tradition and eyewitnesses, these tent-shrines housed relics from Činggis Qan's lifetime, possibly including his and Börte's bodies, as well as ritual implements and the shrine texts. Before the shrine was permanently placed in the Činggis Qan Mausoleum in 1956, they were guarded by men of the Darqads, and moved around by camels to various sites in Ordos. This practice had survived for at least hundreds of years, as the historical texts from the 17th century chronicles tradition and the Jewel Translucent Sutra (see above, under scriptures) depict their use in warfare in the 15-17th centuries. The charisma of Činggis Qan, as embodied in the tent-shrines, were used as a weapon to defeat enemies. In Jewel Translucent Sutra, we also read of attaching defeated peoples - in this case the Uriyangqad - to the shrines as temple slaves. The origin of the Darqad may be traced to this, and other unrecorded by similar circumstances, as the list surnames of the Darqad is remarkably diverse in geographic and political terms.

Reference: Andrews, Peter A.. "The Tents of Chinggis Qan at Ejen Qorugh-a". In *Felt Tents and Pavilions : The Nomadic Tradition and Its Interaction with Princely Tentage.*, Vol. 1. London: Melisende, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is iconography present:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

— Only religious public space

— All public spaces

Notes: The iconography of the Cult of Chinggis Khan can be defined either broadly or narrowly, and their distribution have varied across time. In a sense, the ubiquitous images and replicas of the sülde -- the battle standards constructed of horse hair -- in Mongolian-speaking places can be seen as the cult's iconography. After all, the standard is one of the main objects of worship, or even a deity in its own right, at the cult. However, especially in a modern context, the sülde has become a symbol of the Mongolian state divorced from any association with the cult. Similarly, the prestige of Chinggis Khan and all things related to the Mongol Empire are revered in Mongolian-speaking societies in absence of any reference to the cult per se. In the earliest texts of the Altan Bichig liturgical corpus, the king-list also known as the "Yellow Book" (Šir-a Debter), each imperial ancestor is invoked with an obscure statement ending with the word "labar" or "labir." This term is most likely the Tibetan word "labir," meaning a portrait for worship, or an "icon." The exact ritual usage of this text is now obscure, but the likely context is that libations were offered to each of these former khans, their queens and sons when their portraits were brought forth and propitiated. At the cult itself, however, iconography in the form of

portraits are remembered to have existed until the mid 20th century, until they were destroyed in the Cultural Revolution. Now, various replica have been made by individuals variously associated with the Darqad organization, and some are on display at the museum exhibitions at the Mausoleum. A photographic representation of such a lost portrait does exist for the Cult of Qasar, however. Qasar, the eldest younger-brother of Chinggis Khan, had as a relic a double-sided portrait of him at his cult, which is located in the Darqan-Muuminggan banner, separately from the Ordos shrines. One side was of the 'fierce' Qasar, and the other the 'gentle' manifestation. The photograph was taken and published by the scholar Dorungga, who had visited and studied the shrine in 1958. The tradition holds that the fierce manifestation portrait was done using Qasar's nose-bleed. The use of blood-portraits is a well-known practice in Tibetan-rite Buddhism. Indeed, there are a distinct group of thangkas of the fierce manifestation of Chinggis Khan that in Mongolia in museums, monasteries and in private collection. These thangkas were reproduced in print in G. Nyam-Ochir (2017), and they are thought to bear close relationship to one of the tantric visualization prayers in the Altan Bichig corpus. How these portraits were used in a ritual context is not clear, and have not been studied so far. There are other embodied objects of worship at the Cult of Chinggis Khan, such as the Great Red Horns (musical instrument), The Tall Brown (a large vat for holding sacrificial kumiss), and the White-as-Eggshell (Öndegen Čağan, sacred horse, whose name is most likely a corruption of Ünügün Čağan, the horse that Chinggis Khan took from Dayir Usun in SHM §117).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

– Yes

Notes: The iconography of the Cult of Činggis Qan can be defined either broadly or narrowly, and their distribution have varied across time. In a sense, the ubiquitous images and replicas of the sülde -- the battle standards constructed of horse hair -- in Mongolian-speaking places can be seen as the cult's iconography. After all, the standard is one of the main objects of worship, or even a deity in its own right, at the cult. However, especially in a modern context, the sülde has become a symbol of the Mongolian state divorced from any association with the cult. Similarly, the prestige of Činggis Qan and all things related to the Mongol Empire are revered in Mongolian-speaking societies in absence of any reference to the cult per se. In the earliest texts of the Altan Bičig liturgical corpus, the king-list also known as the "Yellow Book" (Šir-a Debter), each imperial ancestor is invoked with an obscure statement ending with the

word "labar" or "labir." This term is most likely the Tibetan word "labir," meaning a portrait for worship, or an "icon" (See Chapter 3 in Pount, 2023). The exact ritual usage of this text is now obscure, but the likely context is that libations were offered to each of these former khans, their queens and sons when their portraits were brought forth and propitiated. At the cult itself, however, iconography in the form of portraits is remembered to have existed until the mid-20th century, until they were destroyed in the Cultural Revolution. Now, various replicas have been made by individuals variously associated with the Darqad organization, and some are on display at the museum exhibitions at the Mausoleum. A photographic representation of such a lost portrait does exist for the Cult of Qasar, however. Qasar, the eldest younger-brother of Činggis Qan, had as a relic a double-sided portrait of him at his cult, which is located in the Darqan-Muumingġan banner, separately from the Ordos shrines. One side was of the 'fierce' Qasar, and the other the 'gentle' manifestation. The photograph was taken and published by the scholar Dorungga, who had visited and studied the shrine in 1958. The tradition holds that the fierce manifestation portrait was done using Qasar's nosebleed. The use of blood-portraits is a well-known practice in Tibetan-rite Buddhism. Indeed, there are a distinct group of thangkas of the fierce manifestation of Činggis Qan that in Mongolia in museums, monasteries and in private collection. These thangkas were reproduced in print in G. Nyam-Ochir (2017), and they are thought to bear close relationship to one of the tantric visualization prayers in the Altan Bičig corpus. How these portraits were used in a ritual context is not clear and have not been studied so far. There are other embodied objects of worship at the Cult of Činggis Qan, such as the Great Red Horns (musical instrument), The Tall Brown (a large vat for holding sacrificial kumiss), and the White-as-Eggshell (Öndegen Čaġan, sacred horse, whose name is most likely a corruption of Ünügün Čaġan, the horse that Činggis Qan took from Dayir Usun in SHM §117).

Reference: Nyam-Ochir, G.. Chingis Khaany Altan Khörög, Tanin Medekhüin Khyalbarshuulsan Khuvilbar (chinggis Khaan's Iconography). Ulaanbaatar: Mönkhiin Üseg LLC, 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: While the prayers to Cinggis Qan often invoke his horse Öndegen Čaġan 'White as Egg(shell)', his thangkas show him mounted on a green horse. Öndegen Čaġan is one of the deities to whom aspersions are offered.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In the thangkas of Činggis Qan, Buddhist deities and his 'Nine Paladins' (yisün örlögüd) -- historical figures who played important roles during his rise to power -- are placed around him, who is of course the central figure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, there are historical figures alongside guardian deities in the thangkas of Činggis Khan. These are generally identified as: 1. Bo'orču, 2. Mukhali, 3. Jelme, 4. Jebe, 5. Boro'ul, 6. Torkhan Śira, 7. Śigi Khutuġ, 8. Čuu Mergen and 9. Kiraġu the Black, who is otherwise unidentified.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: There are three sites on the bank of the Bayan Čangquǎ river in Ordos upon which the component shrines of the Eight White Tents congregate for ceremonies annually. The same sanctuary is used for three years, and a complete cycle through each site amounts to nine years. Sayinjirgal and Šaraldai (1983) relates that the practice is itself a commemoration of the 81-year cycle that once involved two other locations, called the Great Sanctuary and Middle Sanctuary; both are now in independent Mongolia. The Darqad of Ordos relate that the Kangxi Emperor (r. 1661-1722) of the Qing Empire accidentally came across the migrating cult while on a campaign and became so irritated that he forbade the cult from making rounds across Mongolia. Henceforth, since the Darqad were limited to the Lesser Sanctuary in the Ordos only, they began circulating between three spots at the same location lest the posterity forgets about the migrating tradition.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: In 1935, the famous American traveler and scholar Owen Lattimore traveled to the Cult of Činggis Qan, and wrote about his experience in the book "Mongol Journeys" (1941). From his experience, we know that in the early 20th century, anybody could make a pilgrimage and make an offering to Činggis Qan's spirit. The number of sheep offered as sacrifice is the measure of the grandiosity, and the Darqad are obliged to help the pilgrim perform the ceremonies. We do not know if this practice extended to all persons before this period. However, as a foreigner, Lattimore was able to make the sacrifice, and thereby gain access to view the interior of the shrine. The plates in his book give a rare glimpse of the ceremony as it unfolded.

Reference: Lattimore, Owen. *Mongol Journeys*. New York: Doubleday, Doran & Co., 1941.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The cult's raison d'etre is based on the belief that Činggis Qan's spirit survives through his

personal effects, including the relics and the tent-shrines that house them. However, there is no explicit statement about whether Činggis Qan only obtains his supernatural status post-mortem. That is, Činggis Qan himself is seen to have been born with supernatural qualities, and thus the shrine's divine aspects does not derive from his death. The whole shrine is more accurately seen as efforts to preserve Činggis Qan's divine aura, or in better-known terminology -- his charisma (sülde(r), suu ĵali). For a general treatment of the spirit-body ontology in Mongolia, especially in the context of shamans, see Humphrey (1973).

Reference: Humphrey, Caroline. "Magical Drawings in the Religion of the Buryats". PhD Dissertation, University of Cambridge, 1973.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The spirit-mind is indeed ontologically distinct, since they are invoked by prayers and are asked to perform miracles and affect destinies that the physical bodies cannot accomplish. However, they are also fed with the first fruits of pastoral products, and thus the ability to receive the essence of prayerful intentions embodied in the solid and fluid offerings, as well as incense smoke, indicates the immanent presence of the spirit-mind of Činggis Qan.

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:
– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
– I don't know

Are grave goods present:
– I don't know

Are formal burials present:
– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: There is no one supreme high god in most Mongolian prayers. There are many deities that receive offerings, the foremost of whom are the De'er-e Tngri (Heaven Above) and Do'or-a Etügen (Earth Below). These other deities are often called 'shamanist gods' in the literature, though the category of 'shamanism' itself is problematic.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The main deities to which prayers are directed are indeed historical persons, beginning with Činggis Qan. There are, or had been, several other tent-based cults in Inner Mongolia dedicated to Činggis Qan's wives, mother, brother, daughter-in-law, horse, and other relics that exhibit many of the same characteristics of the Cult, some of which also have their own texts. These are indeed propitiated for blessings and mercy, though no specific reference to rewards or punishment are articulated in the cult's texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Blessings and mercy are the most common objectives of prayers.
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, while there is no one high god, there are many gods mentioned in the prayers at the Cult of Činggis Qan. Of these, the Heaven and Earth maybe seen as holding a special diarchic reign over the entire pantheon, as they are invariably invoked first in the prayers. Moreover, it appears that during the history of the cult, a period of intense ecstatic worshipping practices had taken place, and people had been able to speak in tongues (glossolalia). That is, while experiencing what is usually called an “altered state of mind,” individual uttered incomprehensible words, possibly while performing devotional songs. These were written down and are called the “Twelve Songs of Heaven.” The way these were sung along with the percussion accompaniment were preserved in both manuscript form as well as through performers. In addition, Činggis Qan's standards, his personal belongings, and especially his hearth-fire are worshipped and offered sacrifice as deities. There is, of course, the question of how to classify the reincarnate horses at the shrine. There are the pair of bay horses, who are considered reincarnations of Činggis Qan's horse. There are two horses because one is the current reincarnate, whereas the second, the younger, is the back-up or understudy horse, in case the former dies suddenly. There is also the White-as-Eggshell (Öndegen Čaġan), who is supposed to have come down from heaven to Činggis Qan, and so its reincarnations are continually kept in Eġen Qoro'a. high god, there are many gods mentioned in the prayers at the Cult of Činggis Qan. In addition, Činggis Qan's standards, his personal belongings, and especially his hearth-fire are worshipped and offered sacrifice as deities. There is, of course, the question of how to classify the reincarnate horses at the shrine. There are the pair of bay horses, who are considered reincarnations of Činggis Qan's horse. There are two horses because one is the current reincarnate, whereas the second, the younger, is the back-up or understudy horse, in case the former dies suddenly. There is also the White-as-Eggshell (Öndegen Čaġan), who is supposed to have come down from heaven to Činggis Qan, and so its reincarnations are continually kept in Eġen Qoro'a.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards are a central conceit to the rituals and liturgies at the Cult of Činggis Qan, as the recipients of the shares from sacrificial food are defined as the descendants of not just Činggis Qan, but of other meritorious individuals who helped him create the empire. Moreover, descendants of later individuals who helped maintain and revive the Činggisid lineage are invoked by name, so that the rewards can be eternally bestowed. In addition to these rewards of institutionalized gratitude, the prayer of the cult routinely end with a section named “da’atgal” or “entrustment,” in which the speaker asks for not only blessings and mercy, but rewards for maintaining the sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness¹:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The rewards of the Cult of Činggis Qan are rather typical of the "immanentist" type of religio-political systems, or sacred kingships. In the typology created by Moin and Strathern (2022), the idea of immanence is contrasted with transcendence by its assumption of the ubiquitous presence of meta-humans in the physical world, and the lack of concern for ethical principles in favor of worldly flourishing.

Reference: Moin, A. Azfar, and Alan Strathern, eds.. Sacred Kingship in World History. Edited by A. Azfar Moin and Alan Strathern. Columbia University Press, 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.7312/moin20416>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Preservation of the state/throne for the descendant rulers, which entails worldly pleasures the result from political success and cooperative environmental factors, which result in the pleasures of life, such as wealth, stability, etc.,

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: The cultic texts and their liturgical contexts do not explicitly subscribe any messianic attribute to Činggis Qan, or suggest that he is at all expected to return to this world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: While liturgical texts do not prescribe social norms, the ritual context in many ways can be seen as reinforcing the patriarchic state (törö). See Pount (2020) for an analysis of how masculinity and state authority are reinforced through the rituals for propitiating to Qasar, the younger brother of Chinggis Khan.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Courage (generic):

– I don't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– I don't know

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– I don't know

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– I don't know

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– I don't know

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– I don't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– I don't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: political cohesion

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: Some versions of prayer texts include instructions on using the blood of a human victim. From eyewitness accounts of historical events, notably the capture of the town of Qobdo (Khovd) from the Manchu governor of the Qing Empire in 1912, we know that the heart and blood of vanquished enemies were used to propitiate the sülde. However, it is not clear to what degree the human sacrifice was an

expected part of the Cult of Činggis Qan ceremonies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Meat and alcohol are offered during ceremonies, and fats from meat and butter are sacrificed to the hearth-fire. Alcohol includes distilled spirits made from fermented milk named 'araki' (single-distilled) and 'arĵa' (double distilled). The offerings are distributed to the participants of the ceremony. Moreover, the ritual instructions include the amount of alcohol and horses each sub-group of Mongols have to bring as a form of taxes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

↳ To out-groups:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1000

Notes: At a large scale gathering, the conceit is that the entire Mongol nation has assembled, through their representatives, to commemorate the state founded by Činggis Qan. Descendants of the founding emperor himself as well as the posterity of the meritorious companions that helped him (and his descendant rulers) build or protect the Mongol state are ritually assumed to have shown up to receive their shares from the sacrifices.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The ĵinong, who is a descendant of Činggis Qan who at times co-ruled as a viceroy in Mongolian history, is supposed to supervise the ritual preparations and performances of the Darqad for propriety.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: In the instructions for the Ġaril ceremony, which is a prequel ceremony performed on the night before the White Herd Sačuli (libation sprinkling) ceremony of the summer, one man rides away with a fire-brand and make rounds while those who remain complete other rituals. For a translation of this ritual instruction, see Pount (2023) and Serruys (1984)

Reference: Serruys, Henry. "The Cult of Chinggis-qan: A Mongol Manuscript from Ordos". Zentralasiatische Studien Des Seminars Fr Sprach- Und Kulturwissenschaft Zentralasiens Der Universitt Bonn 17 (1984): 29–62.

Reference: Pount, Dotno. "The Cult of Chinggis Khan in the Dayan Khanid Period". PhD

Dissertation, University of Pennsylvania, 2023.

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: The offering and subsequent consumption of ceremonial liquor is an essential part of the ceremonies at the Cult of Činggis Qan. The liquor are distilled from fermented milk, and thus symbolize the most precious distillate from the fruits of the land and animals. Constituent parts of the kingdom were expected to offer alcohol. The starter culture of the kumiss was another essential part of the ceremony. The shrine as well as the qaġan both had their own herds, and the starter culture for the kumiss would be sprinkled into the sacrificial vat at the ceremony, which is then distributed to the participants at the end. See Chapter 5 and 6 in Pount (2023) for a discussion on the significance of this practice.

Reference: Pount, Dotno. "The Cult of Chinggis Khan in the Dayan Khanid Period". PhD Dissertation, University of Pennsylvania, 2023.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Up to the absorption of Mongolian principalities into the Qing Empire in the 17th century, the ceremony at which khan ascended to the throne was held at the Eight White Tents of Činggis Qan -- or his 'Cult'. Therefore, this was in fact a state-cult. However, the context and reach of the Činggis Qan shrine seems to have shrunk significantly in the 18th century, when it was re-organized as a local shrine in Ordos. However, at this point the society to which it belongs remained to be the entire 'Mongol' people, as conceived in the Qing Empire's context as one of the subject components of its imperial formation. However, because of the partition of Mongolia into three sovereign states in the 20th century, the shrine as it stands today, is largely seen as a local ancestral shrine in the Ordos region, or at

most relevant to Inner Mongolians only.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The rituals are conducted in Mongolian. However, there are certain songs in 'Heaven's Tongue' which are quite obviously glossolalia that were written down in the Mongolian alphabet together with meaningless squiggles.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The number of seasonal, monthly, and daily ceremonies are numerous, and there is a detailed schedule for when to perform which ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mongolia

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1227 CE - 1634 CE

Region: Mongolia

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